

AGILE EDUCATION – A CHALLENGE OR OPPORTUNITY IN POST PANDEMIC UNIVERSITIES?

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper analyzes the possibility of introducing Agile principles and practices in higher education institutions. This concern stems from two main factors: on one hand, the demonstrated efficiency of Agile methodologies when implemented by remote teams and on the other, the growing demand for digitalization in all aspects of daily life.*

Methodology/approach – *A qualitative and ongoing longitudinal study was conducted, which used focus groups of students from the University of Petrosani.*

Findings – *The results of the study highlight a difference between the results obtained when applying the Waterfall approach to the educational process and the Agile methodologies. The differences manifested in the organizational approach, the way that courses were held and the overall results obtained by the students.*

Research limitations/implications – *A quantitative study will follow the qualitative one to find a clear demarcation between Waterfall and Agile in education in terms of performance for a sustainable development of hybrid HE.*

Practical implications – *It is relevant to look at the ways in which HE can be managed from a project management perspective and identify the best suited alternative that can fit the requirements in the current socio-economic context.*

Originality/value – *The paper proposes an approach to the adaptation of Agile for software development in the context of HE.*

Key words: *Higher education, digitalization, hybrid*

Introduction

Project management tools and practices have proven useful for hybrid working arrangements and have the potential ability to answer both the challenges as well as the opportunities of the current context where Higher Education institutions are looking for solutions to digitalization and a transition to a hybrid form of education. Given this aspect, it is relevant to look at the ways in which Higher Education can be managed from a project management perspective and identify the best suited alternative that can fit the requirements of these institutions in the current socio-economic context.

The research introduces a series of notions and approaches to make it possible to create an analogy of the didactic activities deployment in Higher Education (HE) with software development lifecycles (SDLC).

The research is justified by the current trend of HE transformation and digitalization after the pandemic period. Thus, we must admit that the traditional, classic teaching identified with the linear, sequential approach of SDLC did not find us prepared for the changes and challenges brought by the pandemic. As any experience must be used for development, we look at how we can integrate this experience and turn it into something useful and valuable from the perspective of a hybrid, adaptive and flexible HE context.

The paper analyzes the possibility of introducing Agile principles and practices in Higher Education institutions. This concern stems from two main factors: on one hand, the demonstrated efficiency of

Agile methodologies when implemented by remote teams and on the other, the growing demand for digitalization in all aspects of daily life. The study aims to also identify the key differences between the usage and implementation of regular education practices and adoption of Agile inspired methodologies.

The paper presents in the Literature review section the analogy with the SDLC, that was the basis of our approach, and the trends towards Agile approaches in education. Then, following the focus group application in Materials and methods section, Waterfall vs. Agile in hybrid HE Section highlights the usable elements in the deployment of courses with digitization components, concluding with the fact that we must continuously adapt to stay competitive in any field.

Literature review

The evolution of education on the four levels, from Education 1.0 to Education 4.0, was achieved in parallel with the evolution of technology, initially by integrating the specific elements of Web 1.0 and Web 2.0, and currently the trend is to link Education 4.0 to Industry 4.0 as shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1. Education 1.0 towards 4.0

An extremely important milestone in the evolution of education were MOOCs, which existed before the pandemic period, and thus made a substantial contribution during the pandemic both as an alternative educational support and as an experience to learn from. The pandemic meant a pause for reflection for humanity. On the one hand, a conclusion could be that a better use of resources would be needed in any field, implicitly also in education, which should be much better related to the real needs of the society currently in Industry 4.0. However, another important problem rediscovered during the pandemic period is that man needs to interact with other people. Therefore, the digitalization of education must be done with great care to maintain human contact through which society has evolved so far. Speaking of the evolution of technology, we also pointed out the usefulness of SDLCs in Education.

The literature shows that there is interest in approaching Agile principles in education, demonstrated by the publication of the Agile Manifesto in Education (Kamat, 2012) and the application of Agile principles in learning (Lang, 2017). Stewart et al. (2009) showed how agile methods can be applied to many educational projects.

The effectiveness of Agile methodologies applied in online courses was discussed by Noguera et al., (2018). Ahmad et al., (2014), and Heikkila et al., (2016) report the use of Agile tools like the Kanban board in project-based learning (PBL). O. Meerbaum-Salant and O. Hazzan (2010) present the implementation of the “Agile Constructionist Mentoring Methodology” in high school.

The proof of the need to understand agile methodologies is given by the studies that show the fact that the curriculum is updated accordingly. (P. Maher., 2009)

Concerning one of the Agile methodologies, Scrum, there are scientific papers that tried to underline the power of Scrum in education (Zorzo et al., 2013). T. de Jager, (2015) presents the application of the Eduscrum method.

Scrum is mostly adapted in development of projects in undergraduate and graduate levels (R. Romeike and T. Gottel, 2012), (Missiroli, 2017), (Dovleac et al., 2018), (Fuad et al., 2022), but Scrum can also be used in HE projects (Von Wangenheim et al., 2013) and (Steghofer et al., 2017). Also, Scrum was used as a management method in interdisciplinary educational settings (Gestwicki & McNely, 2016) and to teach different subjects (Ringert et al, 2017). Duvall et al. (2017) implemented Scrum methodology in classroom management procedures and Grimheden, (2013) showed that Scrum methodology determined the students to achieve better results.

There are analyzes that compare Agile methodologies and plan-driven practices (P. Rundle and R. Dewar, 2006), respectively Agile methodologies and Waterfall methodology, showing that each of the two approaches has advantages that must be taken into account. There is even a statement made by Missiroli, (2017), according to which "teachers should try to introduce Agile concepts and methodologies, as they might become dominant in the next future", but also a conclusion regarding the introduction of a hybrid methodology, referred to as "Waterscrum" as the first step towards a complete acceptance of Scrum or Agile methods, highly influenced by Industry 4.0 towards Education 4.0.

Materials and Methods

The research methodology is presented in Figure 2, and it can be noticed that it has a strong starting point from the literature review - that highlights the previous approaches on Waterfall and Agile in education and also the values of SDLCs that can be used in education. Based on these, the applied research using the focus group technique provided results regarding the usage of Waterfall versus Agile approach. These, together with the ARACIS standards, have led to the proposal of an approach to deploy teaching activities based on Agile for hybrid HE.

Fig. 2. The research methodology

For the research, the qualitative research tool known as the focus group was implemented in order to analyze the results obtained when using a Waterfall based approach versus an Agile approach in teaching higher education courses. Focus groups have been identified as a reliable source of obtaining data from participants, given the interactions between participants that can elicit data and ideas which might not be uncovered in traditional one-on-one questioning (Plummer-D'Amato, 2008). Furthermore, focus-group interviews, due to its dynamic has often deeper and richer interactions which in turn generate a larger range of data (Rabiee, 2004). Regarding the homogeneity of the focus group and the number of participants, it has been noted that although usually people with similar characteristics are part of the focus group, this is not necessarily relevant or mandatory in all cases, and the decision is highly dependent upon the purpose of the research project (Cameron, 2005). The rule of thumb regarding the number of participants has been pinned down to six to eight participants but the size has been observed to vary from three to twelve participants (Plummer-D'Amato, 2008).

In the case of the current research a total number of 24 participants have been part of four focus groups, each focus group containing six members. The participants were students from two bachelor programs at the Faculty of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering, in the field of Computer and System's Control (Computer Science and Applied Automation). Each bachelor study field had two focus groups, one debating the role, relevance and usefulness of Waterfall based learning and the second one focusing on the same aspects but in the case of Agile driven learning. The moderator for these focus groups has been the teacher that has worked together with the students and held courses for the Project Management discipline that they studied according to the curriculum.

Based on the results obtained by the focus groups and the discussions, along with results obtained by other research and examined during the literature review part of the paper and the quality standards established by ARACIS, the premises for a methodology for planning and delivering courses at HE level have been sketched as it can be observed in Figure 2.

The set of metrics that were used in order to evaluate the results of the conducted activities were based off the metrics described by Missiroli et al, which in their research examined the effects of Waterfall and Agile methodologies on organizing learning activities in the case of K-12 education (Missiroli, Russo, & Ciancarini, 2017) but for the case of the current research these were adapted to fit the qualitative aspect of the latter, as it can be observed in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Metrics

As it can be observed the metrics were concerned not only with the overall product but also the progress and the satisfaction and efficiency of the development team. The main concern in the case of the paper was not just the delivery of a qualitative product but also the experience of the participants and understanding how each development approach can serve them better.

Waterfall vs. Agile in hybrid HE

The Waterfall SDLC is suitable for the first levels of Education in which the contribution of technological tools was quite low, the implementation in the educational process did not allow the significant inclusion of feedback from students, as presented in Figure 4.

Fig.4. Waterfall model in HE

In Agile, even if technology is used to the fullest, the SDLC's scrutiny is driven by the interaction between all the human actors involved. As shown in Figure 5, in order to carry out the didactic activities for a

subject, the phases of the Scrum methodology are followed with their customization on specific HE elements. In each sprint there are tasks to be completed by the students with monitoring by the teaching staff, who train themselves during this period. The obtained results are discussed and are derived the refined requirements for the following tasks.

Fig. 5. Agile model in hybrid HE

An important difference between the two approaches that can be observed in Figures 4 and 5 is that if in the case of the Waterfall approach the level of knowledge is tested only in the last stage - deployment, in the case of the Agile approach there are two points at which the student's level of knowledge and comprehension is tested, in the test phase and in the deployment phase. This can be a starting for a better understanding of the overall performance obtained by the students.

Results

The conducted research can be summarized according to the main parameters as follows: the object of the study was the results obtained by groups of students which followed a Waterfall based approach to learning versus the students that followed an Agile based approach; the purpose of the study was to have an overview of the effects of Waterfall and Agile based learning approaching in HE project-based learning environments; the quality focus consisted of the results obtained by the students with the perspective of both teacher and student perception; the context of the research is applying various development methodologies in order to test relevancy for learning in the case of HE institutions.

Although the main concern of the focus group is to identify the participant's perception regarding a topic and not to obtain a consensus amongst these, the focus groups have unanimously identified Agile based approaches to learning and teaching as more efficient and better fit for the needs of today's generations. The participants also believed that the digitalization effort is a positive aspect of education and can yield plenty of benefits although some drawbacks were identified as well. These concerns could be addressed at least partially by the guidelines provided by ARACIS given the digitalization requirements in HE institutions given the type of subjects and the content that is considered to be taught in a hybrid manner.

The highest level of satisfaction in the case of participants was obtained in the teams that followed the Agile SDLC to their projects and the learning process. These two teams managed to get more work done, have had better results in terms of test scores to test their level of knowledge regarding the Project Management subject, and have emphasized the satisfaction obtained from reaching several small goals and being able to focus on small chums of work with constant feedback, rather than the teams working with the Waterfall SDLC.

The results of the research are in conformance with those of other research conducted on the topic, in terms of the positive feedback provided by both parties (students and teachers) when organizing the learning process in a modern, hybrid and digitalized way, thus showing a clear tendency towards embracing new technologies and methodologies in the educational context.

The results of the focus group together with those of similar previous research created the premises for further development of the research, by analyzing the use of the two methodologies (Waterfall and Agile) for the preparation of teaching activities.

Discussion and conclusions

The results of the study highlight a difference between the results obtained when applying the Waterfall approach to the educational process and the Agile methodologies. The expected differences manifested in the organizational approach, the way that courses were held and the overall results obtained by the students - both as grades at the end of semester but also as projects and assignment created by them. Some of the most significant differences included aspects such as: a different approach to organizing the content of the course through multiple sprints rather than following a traditional syllabus and course outline, the usage of assignments in a modular form rather than delivering a number of courses for each lesson and measuring final results. A quantitative study is expected to follow the qualitative one conducted in the current research paper.

In the current context where a transformation of education towards a hybrid HE is expected, and which will have to represent, for at least a period of time, a new stable state of the educational system, it is very important that the changes made are well founded and sustainable and do not cause uncontrollable instabilities. The educational system of a nation represents the brain of that nation, and what we witness these days should be treated with the same care, thoroughness and precision as a “brain surgery”.

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